

was added absolute ethanol (35 ml) and the separated solid NaCl was removed by filtration. Ethanol was removed from the filtrate under the reduced pressure to get very thick oily pale yellow product (31.7 g) containing 15.4% water (by Karl Fischer); it showed deep red colouration with 2.0% aqueous ferric ammonium sulphate solution. The solid **1** could not be isolated in pure form.

Hexahydro-2H-azepin-2-one oxime (1): A solution of **3** (11.3 g, 0.1 mol), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (6.95 g, 0.1 mol) and NaHCO₃ (8.4 g, 0.1 mol) in 90% aqueous methanol (25 ml) was refluxed with constant stirring for 30 h. The reaction mass was cooled and filtered. From the filtrate, the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to get a pale yellow viscous oil (13.6 g) which showed deep red colouration with 2.0% aqueous ferric ammonium sulphate solution. The viscous oil was contained 6.25% water (by Karl Fischer). Compound **1** could not be isolated in pure form.

Acknowledgement

The author is indebted to Dr. M. H. Mehta, General Manager (Research), to and Dr. M. A. Siddiqui, Superintendent (Process Research) for their keen interest, discussions and suggestions, and thankful to G. S. F. C. Management for facilities.

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Addition-Elimination Reactions of 4- and 6-Chloroindolin-2,3-diones with certain Nucleophilic Reagents†

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Manuscript received 25 March 1988, accepted 29 July 1988

INDOLIN-2, 3-dione and 5,7-substituted-indolin-2,3-dione have been conveniently prepared via Sandmeyer isonitroso synthesis¹. The 3-carbonyl group in indolin-2,3-diones behaves normally

† Dedicated to Prof. W. Pfeleiderer, Universität Konstanz, West Germany on his 60th. birthday, July 22, 1987.

towards nucleophilic reagents and as such numerous addition-elimination reactions have been performed leading to the 3-substituted products²; many such products have shown interesting biological activity³. While nucleophilic reactions on indolin-2,3-diones and 5,7-substituted-indolin-2,3-diones have been reported, not much work has been done on 4- and/or 6-substituted-indolin-2,3-diones, the reason might be the difficulty in getting pure 4- and/or 6-substituted-indolin-2,3-diones via Sandmeyer method. We have now obtained 4- and 6-chloro-indolin-2,3-diones in a pure state by a pH-dependent separation procedure from their mixture⁴.

Nucleophilic attack of benzoic acid hydrazides on **4** and 6-chloroindolin-2,3-diones (**1a**, **b**) underwent smoothly leading to the formation of **4a** and **4d** in excellent yields. **1a** and **1b** were treated with dimethyl sulphate and ethanolic KOH to get the corresponding 1-methyl analogs which were again treated with benzoic acid hydrazides yielding **3a** and **3b**, respectively. Further, Mannich condensation on **4a** and **4b** resulted in the formation of 1-morpholino/piperidino-(methyl-4/6-chloro)-3-(benzoylhydrazano)-2-indolinones (**5a** and **5b**) (Scheme 1). All the compounds have been characterised by elemental analysis and ir and pmr spectral data.

Scheme 1. Reagents. (i) Me₂SO₄/KOH-EtOH, (ii) *o/p*-substituted-benzoylhydrazone, (iii) morpholine/piperidine/HCHO.

The ir spectra of **3-5** showed characteristic bands at 3 150 (NH), 1 700 (C=O), 1 665 (C=O amide) and 1 615 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The pmr spectrum of **5a** sl. no. 11 (Table 1) showed resonance at δ 3.57 (4H, N (CH₂)₂), 4.02 (4H, O(CH₂)₂), 5.2 (2H, NCH₂N) and 7-7.9 (7H, ArH) which is in conformity with the assigned structure.

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 4/6-CHLORO-3-(SUBSTITUTED-BENZOYLHYDRAZONO)-2-INDOLINONES (3-5)*

Sl. no.**	Compd. no.	R	R'	X	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula
1.	3a	OH	H	—	70	230	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl
2.		H	Cl	—	68	215	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂
3.		H	OH	—	75	245	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
4.		H	OCH ₃	—	70	200	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
5.		OH	H	—	67	>280	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
6.	4a	H	Cl	—	73	>280	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂
7.		H	OH	—	67	>280	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
8.		H	OCH ₃	—	76	>280	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
9.	5a	OH	H	O	77	>270	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
10.		OH	H	OH	68	185	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ Cl
11.		H	Cl	O	80	212	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂
12.		H	Cl	OH	74	230	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ Cl ₂
13.		H	OH	O	70	210	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
14.		H	OH	OH	73	200	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ Cl
15.		H	OCH ₃	O	74	215	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
16.		H	OCH ₃	OH	74	197	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ Cl
17.	3b	OH	H	—	65	290	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
18.		H	OH	—	72	230	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
19.		H	OCH ₃	—	74	270	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
20.	4b	OH	H	—	64	>280	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
21.		H	Cl	—	60	>280	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂
22.		H	OH	—	63	>280	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
23.		H	OCH ₃	—	70	>280	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
24.	5b	OH	H	O	65	170	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
25.		H	Cl	O	60	240	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂
26.		H	Cl	OH	62	235	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ Cl ₂
27.		H	OH	O	64	260	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
28.		H	OH	CH ₃	70	225	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
29.		H	OCH ₃	O	68	280	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ Cl
30.		H	OCH ₃	CH ₃	70	215	C ₁₉ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄ Cl

* All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H analysis; **Y = 4-Cl for sl. nos. 1-6 and 6-Cl for sl. nos. 17-30.

Experimental

4-Chloro-1-methylindolin-2,3-dione (2a): To a suspension of **1a** (5.0 g) in methanol (75 ml), 10% methanolic KOH (25 ml) was added dropwise with stirring in ~20 min. To the resulting deep purple solution/suspension, freshly distilled dimethyl sulphate (3.25 ml) was added and the mixture shaken for 30 min. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate concentrated. The resulting residue was dissolved in warm water (20 ml) and the concentrated solution was added to it and then heated. On cooling, the product separated as orange needles (**2a**; 78%), m.p. 190° (lit.⁵ 191°).

6-Chloro-1-methyl-indolin-2,3-dione (2b): It was prepared using the same procedure as described above, m.p. 170°.

4-Chloro-1-methyl-3-(substituted-benzoylhydrazono)-2-indolinones (3a): 4-Chloro-1-methylindolin-2,3-dione (0.005 mol) was refluxed with *o/p*-substituted-benzoylhydrazines (0.005 mol) in methanol (10 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (1 drop) on a water-bath for 3-4 h. The resulting orange-red crystals separated on cooling were filtered and dried (Table 1).

6-Chloro-1-methyl-3-(substituted-benzoylhydrazono)-2-indolinones (3b): It was prepared by condensing 6-chloro-1-methylindolin-2,3-dione (0.005 mol) and *o/p*-substituted-benzoylhydrazines (0.005 mol) in methanol (10 ml) containing glacial

acetic acid (1 drop) on a water-bath for 3-4 h. The resulting orange-red crystals separated on cooling were filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallised from methanol (Table 1). The compound **5a**, sl. no 9 (Table 1) showed pmr peaks at δ 2.64 (4H, N(CH₂)₂), 3.69 (4H, O(CH₂)₂); 4.50 (2H, NCH₂N), 6.8-7.7 (7H, ArH), 11.76 (1H, OH phenolic disappeared on D₂O exchange) and 14.11 (4H, NH disappeared on D₂O exchange).

4-Chloro-3-(substituted-benzoylhydrazono)-2-indolinones (4a): A mixture of 4-chloroisatin (1.81 g, 0.01 mol) and benzoic acid hydrazide (1.36 g, 0.01 mol) in methanol (15 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (1 drop), was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the resulting solid was filtered and washed with methanol.

Other compounds were prepared by the same method using different benzoic acid hydrazides as shown in Table 1.

6-Chloro-3-(substituted benzoyl hydrazono)-2-indolinones (4b): It was prepared by using 6-chloroisatin and different benzoic acid hydrazides as shown in Table 1.

4-Chloro-1-morpholino/piperidino-methyl-3-(substituted-benzoylhydrazono)-2-indolinones (5a): 4-Chloro-3-benzoylhydrazono-2-indolinone (0.01 mol) suspended in DMF (20 ml) was warmed on a water-bath and then formalin (1 ml) and morpholine

(1 ml) were added to it with vigorous stirring, and the mixture was then left at room temperature. The resulting crystals were filtered, washed with methanol, dried at room temperature and recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°).

The same procedure was followed to synthesise the other morpholino/piperidino-methyl analogs (Table 1).

6-Chloro-1-morpholino/piperidino-methyl-3-(substituted-benzoylhydrazono)-2-indolinones (5b): It was prepared by the above method using 6-chloro-3-(substituted-benzoylhydrazono)-2-indolinones (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Head of the Chemistry Department for facilities. Thanks are also due to Dr. R. S. Kapil and Prof S. P. Singh for analytical/spectral data.

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Studies on Quinazoline and Mercaptoquinazoline. Preparation and Antibacterial Activity of 2-(2'-Styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4-(arylyureido)-6-chloro-s-triazazine and 2-(2'-Mercapto-3'-(4''-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4,6-bis(arylyureido)-s-triazazine

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Manuscript received 24 December 1987, revised 3 June 1988, accepted 2 August 1988

QUINAZOLINE derivatives exhibit various physiological activities¹. It was shown that the introduction of SH group inhibits the proteolytic and insecticidal activities². The urea derivatives possess many therapeutic activities³. Several workers have investigated s-triazazine nucleus as potential therapeutic agents and fungicides⁴.

In order to synthesise more active compounds, we have synthesised 2-(2'-styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4-(arylyureido)-6-chloro-s-triazazine (1)⁵ and

2-[2'-mercapto-3'-(4''-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino]-4,6-bis(arylyureido)-s-triazazine (2)⁶ derivatives.

Experimental

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

2-(2'-Styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4,6-dichloro-s-triazazine: 2-Styryl-6-amino-4-oxoquinazoline (2.63 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone was added in a well-stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone. The reaction mixture was stirred at 0–5° for 2 h maintaining the pH at 7. It was then poured on crushed ice, filtered and the product crystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 340°.

General method of preparation of 2-(2'-styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4-(arylyureido)-s-triazazine (1): 2-(2'-Styryl-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino)-4,6-dichloro-s-triazazine (0.01 mol) and arylureas (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone were refluxed at 80–90° for 3 h maintaining the pH at 7. The mixture was then poured on crushed ice, filtered, and the products were crystallised from ethanol, (70–85%), melting points of the compounds, R=phenyl, 235°; o-tolyl, 242°; m-tolyl, 223°; p-tolyl, 205°; o-nitrophenyl, 196°; m-nitrophenyl, 200°; p-nitrophenyl, 238°; o-chlorophenyl, 246°; m-chlorophenyl, 282°; p-chlorophenyl, 296°; ν_{\max} 1 430–1 440 (NH), 1 660–1 670 (CO), 1 020–1 040 (CH=CH) and 800–810 cm^{-1} (C_2N_2).

2-[2'-Mercapto-3'-(4''-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino]-4,6-dichloro-s-triazazine: 2-Mercapto-(4'-methylphenyl)-6-amino-4-oxoquinazoline (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone was added to a well-stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (0.01 mol) dissolved in acetone. The reaction mixture was stirred at 0–5° for 2 h maintaining the pH at 7. It was then poured on crushed ice, filtered and crystallised from ethanol, (81%), m.p. 334°.

General method of preparation of 2-[2'-mercapto-3'-(4''-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino]-4,6-bis(arylyureido)-s-triazazine: A mixture of 2-[2'-mercapto-3'-(4''-methylphenyl)-4'-oxoquinazolino-6'-ylamino]-4,6-dichloro-s-triazazine (0.01 mol) and arylureas (0.02 mol) dissolved in acetone was refluxed at 80–90° for 3 h maintaining the pH at 7. The